

Cost-effectiveness analysis with decision analysis networks^{*†}

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Abstract

Decision analysis networks (DANs) are a new type of probabilistic graphical model. Like influence diagrams (IDs), they are much more compact and easier to build than decision trees and can represent conditional independencies, but they can also represent problems involving partial orderings of the decisions (order asymmetry) and other types of asymmetry. Given that DANs can solve symmetric problems as easily and as efficiently as IDs, and are more appropriate for asymmetric problems—which include virtually all real-world problems—DANs might replace IDs as the standard type of probabilistic graphical model for decision analysis. In particular, they can be used to perform cost-effectiveness analyses (CEAs), which are used increasingly in medicine to determine whether the health benefit of an intervention is worth the economic cost.

Keywords: Decision analysis networks, decision trees, influence diagrams, probabilistic graphical models, medical decision making, cost-effectiveness analysis.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Probabilistic models for decision analysis

A probabilistic graphical model (PGM) (Koller & Friedman, 2009) consists of a probability distribution P , defined on a set of variables \mathbf{X} , and a graph, such that each node in the graph represents a variable and—roughly speaking—edges represent dependencies among those variables; more precisely, every absent link denotes a relation of probabilistic independence. PGMs include Bayesian networks (Pearl, 1988), influence diagrams (IDs) (Howard & Matheson, 1984), and several types of Markov models, and have been extensively studied in the field of artificial intelligence.

The two formalisms most widely used for the representation and analysis of decision problems are decision trees (DTs) (Raiffa & Schlaifer, 1961) and IDs. DTs have the advantage of almost absolute flexibility, but also have several drawbacks, mainly that their size grows exponentially: an ID whose chance and decision nodes represent n binary variables is equivalent to a decision tree with around 2^n leaves. In contrast, IDs have the advantages of being very compact, easily representing conditional independence, and using direct probabilities, which allows them to address much larger problems. For example, Luque et al. (2016) built Mediastinet, an ID for finding the optimal sequence of tests for the mediastinal staging of non-small cell lung cancer. Building an equivalent DT would have been impossible because the tree would have more than 10,000 branches.

The main limitation of IDs is that they can only represent symmetric decision problems (Díez et al., 2018). There is *domain asymmetry* when the value taken by a variable X restricts the values that variable Y can take (for example, the result of a test Y is positive or negative only when the decision X is to do the test); there is *information asymmetry* when a variable Y (for example, the result of a test) is observed for some values of a variable X (in our example, when $X =$ ‘do the test’) but not for others (‘do not test’); and there is *order asymmetry* when the decisions can be made in different orders (for example, when the order of several tests is not set a priori). Virtually all real-world problems are asymmetric. For example, when addressing the mediastinal staging of lung cancer the pneumologist was uncertain about the optimal ordering of the tests.

For this reason, Díez et al. (2018) introduced *decision analysis networks* (DANs), which, in addition to representing all symmetric problems as easily as with IDs, can also represent and solve asymmetric problems. In particular, the DAN version of Mediastinet did not need a total ordering of the tests.

1.2 The difficulty of cost-effectiveness analysis

Due to the rapid increase of medical expenditures in all countries, every health system must analyse whether the benefit of each intervention outweighs its economic cost. Cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA), the most common type of economic evaluation, is based on the notion of *net monetary benefit* (Stinnett

& Mullahy, 1998),

$$NMB(\lambda) = \lambda \cdot e - c, \quad (1)$$

where e is the average effectiveness and c the average cost of the intervention for the subpopulation of interest. The parameter λ , usually called *willingness to pay* or *cost-effectiveness threshold*, converts effectiveness into a monetary scale. It takes values on the set of positive real numbers, i.e., on the interval $(0, +\infty)$, and is measured in effectiveness units divided by cost units; for example, in dollars per death avoided or euros per quality-adjusted life year (QALY) (Weinstein et al., 2009).

When there are several incompatible interventions for a problem, CEA looks for the one having the highest NMB. If no intervention dominates the others (i.e., no one is more effective and cheaper than the others), the optimal intervention depends on λ .

As the willingness to pay is specific for each decision maker—in this case, for each health system—and often imprecise or uncertain, CEA must consider all the possible values of λ . It may conclude, for example, that when the willingness to pay is below 35,847 euros per QALY the optimal intervention would be not to do anything, and when it is above that threshold the optimal intervention would be to do a test and, if positive, apply a certain therapy.

The main method that health economists use for CEA are DTs (Drummond et al., 2015), in spite of their serious limitations. In particular, the size of the tree, which grows exponentially in the unicriterion case, as mentioned above, grows much faster for CEA, because the standard algorithm (Raiffa & Schlaifer, 1961) cannot evaluate decision trees with embedded decision nodes, which are those other than the root of the tree (Kuntz & Weinstein, 2001; Arias & Díez, 2014).

Despite of the increasing importance of economic evaluations for medical decision making, artificial intelligence has not addressed this problem until very recently, due to the lack of appropriate tools. In particular, the standard algorithms for IDs (Olmsted, 1983; Shachter, 1986; Luque & Díez, 2010) could only evaluate unicriterion models, so they were unable to perform CEA. For example, they could evaluate the ID Mediastinet for each single value of λ , but they could not find a set of n thresholds delimiting $n + 1$ intervals for the willingness to pay, with an optimal intervention for each interval. In contrast, the algorithm by Arias & Díez (2015) was able to perform CEA with IDs, thus being the first application of an AI method to the economic evaluation of health technologies.

However, that algorithm still had one drawback, stemming from the inability of IDs to represent asymmetric problems, so every ID requires a total ordering of the decisions. In the case of mediastinal staging of lung cancer, the problem was that neither the pulmonologist could determine the optimal order with certainty, nor the ID was able to find it.

2 Cost-effectiveness analysis with DANs

The problem was solved by designing a CEA algorithm for DANs (Díez et al., 2021) that combined the method for evaluating unicriterion DANs (Díez et al., 2018) with the CEA algorithm for decision trees with embedded decision nodes (Arias & Díez, 2011). The former generates a tree of symmetric DANs and the latter evaluates it from the leaves to the root, generating a set of thresholds and intervals for the willingness to pay, each interval having a value of effectiveness, a cost, and an optimal intervention, just as in the evaluation of IDs (Arias & Díez, 2015). The basic idea was straightforward, but integrating those techniques required significant effort.

DANs and the CEA algorithms have been implemented in OpenMarkov, an open-source tool for building and evaluating probabilistic graphical models, which has been used for teaching and research in more than 30 countries, from top universities, research centres of the US Government and large companies, to teachers and students in poor countries, who could not afford the price of commercial products for probabilistic graphical models or for cost-effectiveness analysis.

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